

Workshop Report

**Report of activities, methods, and results from:
Assessing Nature Based Solutions to Mitigate Flood Impacts and
Enhance Resilience Workshop**

April 17, 2023
Five Rivers Delta Resource Center
Spanish Fort, AL

Assessing Nature Based Solutions to Mitigate Flood Impacts and Enhance Resilience

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Workshop Summary

The goal of this project is to advance our understanding about the effectiveness of natural features and nature-based solutions (NBS) in mitigating the risk of compound flooding around Mobile Bay, AL. The effort focuses on coupling hydrologic models of Mobile Bay with the National Water Model and incorporating effects of flood mitigation strategies, particularly NBS, into the coupled models to inform coastal planning and decision-making. The project team is using a stakeholder-driven process to shape and inform the research and modeling.

The project team and coastal stakeholders met in-person for the first time on April 17, 2023, to discuss project goals, stakeholder needs, and exchange knowledge. Stakeholders represented a broad range of entities from federal, state, and municipal organizations in addition to non-profit organizations. Members of the project team were in attendance including modelers, hydrologists, social scientists, and ecologists.

Workshop attendees were provided with information on the project goals, objectives, methods, and potential outputs. They were also given opportunities to express their planning and management needs. Stakeholder input was requested for topics including storm events to use for model calibration, locations flooding occurs, locations flood mitigation projects will be or have been implemented, project design life, surge/rainfall combinations of interest, and how project outputs can be used.

PowerPoint presentations from the project team, with time for participant questions and answers, were used to highlight background information, research methods, and modeling capabilities. Various interactive and collaborative exercises were also used to give the project team a better understanding of stakeholder needs and priorities. These include an icebreaker activity, digital and print mapping exercises, whole-group facilitated discussions, group polling, and opportunities to indicate needs or interests on charts/graphs.

Stakeholder feedback will also inform the next steps for the project team. Workshop attendees expressed positive opinions of the workshop and indicated that they departed with an understanding of project goals, objectives, and light technical knowledge of the modeling process.

Workshop Objectives

- Coastal stewards understand the CIROH project goals, objectives, timeline, and their role in shaping the project outputs
- To understand stakeholder flood risk perceptions and potential shifts in risk perceptions
- To understand stakeholder perspectives and potential shifts in perspectives regarding NBSs
- To learn what types of flood events are of interest to stakeholders, and where these are occurring
- To understand the management needs of the stakeholders for future planning/development
- To understand the future conditions and timescales for which stakeholders are planning
- Stakeholders understand modeling constraints surrounding flood mitigation strategies
- Modeling team learns from the stakeholders' firsthand experience with floods around Mobile Bay and collect information about historic flood hotspots to ground truth their numerical models
- To identify mitigation strategies stakeholders plan to or would like to implement and locations where these will/would be implemented
- To understand metrics that indicate a mitigation strategy is successful
- To identify opportunities for collaboration around data and resource sharing
- To solicit input on what types of outputs/products are most useful to stakeholders

Organizations Represented

ADCNR State Lands	Mobile Bay National Estuary Program
AL Association of Conservation Districts	MSU Coastal Conservation and Restoration
AL Department of Transportation	Mississippi-Alabama Sea Grant
Alabama Port Authority	NOAA *
Baldwin County	Program for Local Adaptation to Climate Effects *
Bon Secour NWR - USFWS	South Alabama Land Trust
City of Foley	The Nature Conservancy
City of Mobile	The University of Alabama *
Cooperative Institute for Research Operations in Hydrology	The Water Institute *
Fowl River Area Civic Association	US Army Corps of Engineers
Mississippi State University Extension *	Weeks Bay NERR

*denotes affiliation with project team

Workshop Activities and Content

Arrival and Pre-Survey

Workshop attendees were greeted, directed to sign-in, and asked to find the folder with their name on it that served as a place card. The folder contained a pre-survey, agenda, workshop evaluation and a post-survey (Appendix A). Project team members were circulating among the group, requesting attendees take the pre-survey. Attendees were given the pre-survey prior to engaging in any workshop activities to provide a baseline of knowledge and perceptions.

Welcome, Objectives, and Introductions

Lead PI, Dr. Hamed Moftakhari welcomed everyone to the workshop and introduced Dr. Renee Collini as the lead facilitator. Renee reviewed the agenda for the day, laid out ground rules, defined the marina and segued into the ice breaker.

Ice Breaker, Rainfall Events Discussion

Participants were given the ice-breaker sheet (Appendix A) and instructed to work in pairs or groups of 3 to complete storm event trivia using a word bank. Working in small groups allowed participants to get comfortable with talking to one another and get them in a frame of mind for the subsequent rainfall event discussion. The storm events in the activity were predominantly recent storms that impacted Mobile, AL and surrounding areas so the local stakeholders might have recollections of these events. A few questions pertained to nation-wide events. Renee introduced Ms. Larisa Lee to review the answers to the ice breaker. Larisa provided the answers and highlighted certain features of the storm events discussed. For example, she drew attention to the fact that lower category hurricanes that move slowly (e.g., Sally, 2020) or are associated with higher-than-normal rainfall (e.g., Danny, 1997) can be associated with intense flooding. Also, ordinary rain events can lead to flooding as intense as named storms, especially when they occur in quick succession.

The ice breaker led into a discussion about the rainfall and storm events stakeholders are more interested in and would like used for model calibration. The group also provided input by suggesting other rain events not mentioned on the Ice Breaker, such as a December 2016 rainfall that impacted Baldwin County. Attendees suggested that consecutive rain events and storms that exceed predictions or intensify unexpectedly just prior to making landfall are a priority.

Discussion Key Points

Interest In:

- Storms that deviate from predictions
- Common extreme rainfall (non-named storms)
- Consecutive days of rainfall

Suggested for Model Calibration/Validation:

- Sally (2020)
- Zeta (2020)
- Danny (1997)
- April 2014 rainfall event
- December 2016 rainfall event

Project Overview

Hamed provided a project overview (Fig 1, PowerPoint found in Appendix B). He described the benefits of wetlands and provided data on the area of marshes lost annually in Mobile Bay. He then discussed the main objectives of the project: to quantify the performance of natural features and NBSs and to provide actionable information to decision makers. A flow chart was used to depict the stages of the project and then Hamed opened the floor to questions.

A question was posed about the availability of funding to implement the NBSs identified, and Renee clarified the distinction between implementing the projects on the ground versus implementing them in the models. The topic shifted to water management plans and whether current watershed management plans can be incorporated and that draft language to put into watershed management plans would be a valuable output. Suggestions arose about considering stormwater management and water quality. A comment was offered to make the distinction between combined flooding and compound flooding, this was tabled until the compound flooding discussion later in the day.

Figure 1: Hamed providing a project overview

Flood Mapping

The attendees engaged in a table-level activity, Survey123 was used to allow participants to indicate areas where flooding occurs. Each table had a facilitator that drew the flooding on the map and entered the responses to questions (Fig 2). After the small groups entered the flooding data, Larisa displayed the digital map with the areas of flooding drawn on it and asked if there were any other additions that needed to be made. A few more suggestions were added into the survey and populated on the projected map. Figure 3 shows the map of Mobile Bay with flood locations marked, see Appendix C for zoomed-in views.

Figure 2 Attendees Engaged in Mapping Activities

Figure 3 map of Mobile Bay with drawn flood locations

Defining Compound Flooding

To make sure the group was operating under the same definitions of compound flooding, Hamed gave a PowerPoint presentation defining compound flooding. He first discussed background information about the catastrophic effects of flooding and importance of reliable flood modeling data. Hurricane Harvey provided an example of a situation where around half of the damaged properties were located outside the 500-year floodplain. Multiple flood drivers occurring simultaneously, or in quick succession are not additive in their effects. Hamed described probabilistic modeling and process-based modeling then wrapped up with a question-and-answer session.

After Hamed's presentation defining compound flooding (slides in appendix B), Renee facilitated an activity where a blank graph was presented to the group with coastal flooding/surge on the X axis and Rainfall on the Y axis. Renee solicited input from the group to set the low and high boundaries on each axis. The group offered suggestions to set the values based on a variety of factors like design standards, affordability, or availability of data.

Figure 4: Marking on the Compound Flooding graph

Following the presentation, Renee led an activity where the group provided input to collectively decide on what combinations of surge and rainfall return periods to prioritize (see Appendix C for in-depth review of activity and discussion). A graph with coastal flooding/surge on the X axis and rainfall on the Y axis with no numerical values on the axes was presented to the group. Input was taken to fill in the numerical values on the axes with return periods for each flooding type. Participants were given three sticker dots to place on the graph (Fig 4): 1 red for high-priority, 1 yellow for medium priority, and 1 green for lower priority. After participants placed dots on their desired return period combinations, Renee led a discussion to talk through the responses.

There was some variation among the group around where priorities lie (Fig 5), but there was collective agreement over interest in the 50-year surge and 50-year rainfall levels (middle of the graph). Strong interest was evident for a lower surge value, approx. 5-10 year and a ~50 year return period on rainfall.

Figure 5: Graph with return periods for coastal flooding on X axis and return periods for rainfall on the Y axis.

Compound Combinations of Interest

- 50-year coastal flooding and 50-year rainfall
- ~10-year coastal flooding and 50-year rainfall
- ~25-year coastal flooding and ~25-year rainfall
- Low, ~5-year coastal and ~5-year rainfall

Future Planning

An activity was led that allowed attendees to use sticker dots to indicate what design life, sea-level rise (SLR) trends, and increases in extreme rainfall events they are planning for in their projects (Fig 6). Renee first introduced the line charts and explained what attendees would be doing. She then showed sea level rise projections from the NASA-hosted Interagency SLR scenario tool that showed the locally-specific SLR scenarios for coastal Alabama and the observed rates of SLR from the Dauphin Island tide station (Fig 7). Participants were asked to indicate two SLR trends for which they are planning.

Figure 6: Participants placing stickers on charts

Because extrapolations of observed data only extend to the year 2050 and the other scenarios continue beyond 2050 stakeholders were asked to indicate the SLR projection they were interested in for the timeframe up to 2050 and then after 2050 (Fig 8).

Figure 7: Renee showing SLR scenario tool

Figure 8: Chart showing SLR trends for which stakeholders are planning

For planning up to 2050, there was an even spread of dots placed at Intermediate-High, High, and Current Trend with a few dots placed at Intermediate. For beyond 2050, most respondents selected Intermediate-High or High, with few responses for lower scenarios.

Based on information learned during the presentation, stakeholders were asked to indicate the percent increase in extreme rainfall they are interested in. Participants were given options of 10%, 15%, and 20% given projected increases in the region. Most responses were for 10% or 15% with very few responses for higher percent increases (Fig 9).

Figure 9: Percent increase in extreme rainfall events for which stakeholders are planning.

Similarly, stakeholders were asked about the design life or planning horizons of interest (Fig 10). The range of options spanned 10 years to 50 years. It was brought up that in some fields, the projects are closer to 100-year, or at minimum 75-year so the range was extended.

Figure 10: Project design life for which stakeholders are planning

The line charting exercises were followed by a short discussion to glean any additional input. General trends on each chart were pointed out to the group.

Future Planning Summary

Percent of respondents that selected each option

Mitigation Strategies

Dr. Nate Jones started out the section with a PowerPoint presentation (Appendix B) describing flood mitigation strategies, and Nature Based Solutions as flood mitigation strategies. He described what types of mitigation strategies the project team would want more information about. During the question-and-answer session following the presentation, some questions and discussion about project size ensued. Nate made it clear that long skinny features, as some NBSs in the area are, would not be a limitation to modeling if they were a certain length. Another question was asked to clarify the main

goal of the project, asking if the goal was to develop NBSs in and around Mobile Bay to combat the effects of compound flooding. The clarification was made that the project goal is to evaluate, rather than develop NBSs around Mobile Bay.

Mitigation Mapping

After the introduction to mitigation strategies and NBSs, the group engaged in a follow up mapping activity (Fig 11). Large, printed maps of the perimeter of Mobile Bay were displayed. Participants were asked to mark past mitigation projects with blue dots, future mitigation projects with pink dots, changes in land use or zoning with green dots, and areas they need more information with orange dots. For each dot, participants provided details about the feature including the date of implementation, size, criteria for success, what it would look like if no action is taken, and what pre- or post-monitoring is involved. More than 50 points were identified across all the maps. Map points from this exercise along with points marked in the flood location Survey123 mapping exercise were used in the development of a GIS web map.

Figure 11: Attendees marking locations on maps

Outputs/End Products

Discussions were around what types of outputs or end products would be most useful to local stakeholders. Stakeholders were given time to reflect on their own and write down what they could do with the information the project will produce, how the information should/could be packaged, where they get this kind of information currently, and how it could integrate with what currently exists (Fig 12). A group discussion was held to review common themes between responses. Discussion details can be found in Appendix C.

Figure 12: Chart showing responses to questions

Outputs Summary

What could you do with this info?

- Management
- Project prioritization
- Communication
- Project justification/leverage

How do you need this info packaged?

- Maps
- Shapefiles
- Simulations
- Extension materials

Where do you get this info now?

- Other professionals
- Online tools
- FEMA, ADECA flood maps
- USGS/USFWS climate models

How can this integrate with what currently exists?

- Add to county websites

Opportunities for Collaboration and Data Sharing

A whole-group facilitated discussion was held to assist attendees in considering opportunities for collaboration and data sharing. The maps from the previous mapping exercise were on display around the room to allow attendees to see where others are implementing projects or have already done projects. Dr. Julia Cherry described the type of data she would need to collect, such as elevation data, biomass along an elevation gradient, and species composition. Individuals from The Nature Conservancy, Mississippi State University Extension, and the National Estuary Program described data they have on file and are willing to share.

Wrap-up

A post-workshop survey and a workshop evaluation ([here](#)) was in each attendee's folder. Renee encouraged attendees to fill out both questionnaires. The survey was nearly identical to the pre-survey attendees were asked to fill out at the beginning of the workshop. The workshop evaluation pertained to the workshop experience, what participants liked or disliked and solicited suggestions for improvement. Renee thanked guests for attending and providing thoughtful input throughout the day.

Workshop Evaluation Survey Results

Workshop Evaluation Survey Results:

Total Responses 18

A printed workshop evaluation, found in Appendix A, was included in the workshop folders for all attendees, both stakeholders and the project team. Attendees were encouraged to complete the survey during the wrap-up phase of the workshop. The survey included 19 matrix-table Likert scale questions and 4 open-ended response questions. Responses to matrix questions are shown below:

Respondents ranked the workshop experience and content highly, with 100% of respondents ranking the “overall workshop experience” favorably. Open-ended questions allowed participants to provide input on what was most useful, least useful, what would improve the workshop, and any questions they have after participating in the workshop. Respondents most liked the interactivity, diversity of viewpoints, feeling that their needs are heard, ability to provide input on the front-end of the project, and applicability of outputs. Least useful aspects of the workshop were descriptions of NBSs, this is possibly because many attendees are already familiar with and already involved in projects related to NBSs. Suggested improvements include providing a project overview prior to the workshop and addition of more small group work. There were both requests for more and requests for less introductory information pertaining to NBS.

Appendix A: Workshop Materials

Agenda:

Assessing Nature Based Solutions to Mitigate Flood Impacts and Enhance Resilience

Mobile Bay Compound Flood Modeling Project
30945 Five Rivers Boulevard, Spanish Fort, AL 36527
April 17, 2023

Objectives

- Attendees understand the CIROH project goals, objectives, timeline, and their role in shaping the project outputs
- To gather input on flood events that are of interest to attendees, and where these are occurring
- To understand management needs of attendees for future planning/development
- To understand the future conditions and timescales for which attendees are planning
- Attendees understand modeling constraints regarding flood mitigation strategies
- To identify mitigation strategies that will be implemented and locations where these will be implemented
- To understand metrics that indicate a mitigation strategy is successful
- To identify opportunities for collaboration around data and resource sharing
- To solicit input on what types of outputs/products are most useful to attendees

Agenda

8:30 am	Arrival, Check-in, Survey
9:00 am	Welcome, Workshop Objectives, and Introductions <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Welcome to the workshop• Introduce workshop team• Review agenda, logistics, ground rules
9:15 am	Ice Breaker, Rainfall Event Discussion* <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ice Breaker in pairs or 3s• Rainfall event discussion
9:50 am	Project Overview

- Project goals, objectives, and timeline
- Incorporating social science

10:10 am	10 Minute Break
10:20 am	Flood Events* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flood mapping activity
11:05 am	Defining Compound Flooding* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation on compound flooding ● Graph exercise
12:05 am	Lunch
12:50 pm	Future Planning, Timescales <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Graphing activities ● Group discussion
1:30 pm	Mitigation Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation on mitigation strategies ● Model constraints, what can be used
1:45 pm	Mitigation Mapping <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mapping activities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mapping upcoming mitigation projects 2. Mapping past mitigation projects 3. Land use changes 4. Information gap mapping
2:55 pm	10 Minute Break
3:05 pm	Opportunities for Collaboration* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● View maps as a group ● Group discussion on collaboration opportunities
3:35 pm	Outputs and End Products* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How can outputs from this project be used?
3:30 pm	Wrap-up <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recap the day ● Survey ● Workshop Evaluation
4:30 pm	Adjourn

*Indicates sections that may be audio recorded

Ice Breaker Activity:

Ice Breaker:

Fill in the blanks using the word bank below. Some answers may be used more than once, some not at all.

<p>1. How many category 5 hurricanes occurred between 2000 and 2005? _____</p>	<p>2. Some areas between Mobile, AL and Pensacola, FL documented 20" of rainfall from this hurricane: _____</p>	<p>3. Of the 10 highest rainfall events in the last 70 years, how many are not named storms? _____</p>	<p>4. This recent hurricane was the first to make landfall in Alabama since Ivan in 2004: _____</p>
<p>5. This cat 5 hurricane weakened to a cat 3 prior to making landfall, it brought 14' of surge in Orange Beach: _____</p>	<p>6. Name all the category 5 hurricanes that occurred during the 2005 season: _____, _____, _____, _____</p>	<p>7. Of the three highest rain events in the last 70 years, how many are NOT named storms? _____</p>	<p>8. An estimated _____ inches of rainfall was documented during a rain event that occurred April 29, 2014.</p>
<p>9. Though it was a small cat 1, dopplers estimate the rainfall from hurricane _____ to be _____ inches over Mobile Bay near Dauphin Island, with 25.9" falling over a 7-hour timeframe.</p>	<p>10. Hurricane _____ in 1995 made landfall as a cat 3 near Pensacola Beach, FL with a 20' storm surge. 7.4" of rainfall was documented in Mobile, AL and 19.42" of rainfall in Brewton, AL (about 60 miles N of the coast).</p>	<p>11. A heavy Mobile, AL rain event in September of _____ brought 5.69" of rainfall one day followed by 7.5" the next day.</p>	<p>12. After making landfall in Gulf Shores, AL as a cat 3, this hurricane travelled northeast through NC and VA, south through the Atlantic, west across FL and re-strengthened to a tropical storm where it hit southwestern LA as a tropical depression: _____</p>

Dennis	Danny	Sally
43	1	Andrew
Harvey	Michael	Opal
11.23	5	8
Rita	Katrina	2015
Emily	Ivan	Wilma

Participant Evaluation Survey:

Workshop Evaluation
Assessing Nature Based Solutions to Mitigate Flood Impacts and Enhance Resilience
 Mobile Bay Compound Flood Modeling Project

1) Please provide your thoughts on the following aspects of today’s workshop

	Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
Workshop Content	1	2	3	4	5
Workshop Format	1	2	3	4	5
Workshop Pace	1	2	3	4	5
Workshop Time Length	1	2	3	4	5
Level of Detail Provided	1	2	3	4	5
Workshop Location	1	2	3	4	5
Opportunities to provide input	1	2	3	4	5
Opportunities to communicate my needs	1	2	3	4	5
Opportunities to ask questions	1	2	3	4	5
Knowledge and Communication skills of presenters	1	2	3	4	5
Refreshments	1	2	3	4	5
Overall workshop experience	1	2	3	4	5

2) Please provide your thoughts about the following aspects of today's workshop:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know
This workshop was a good use of my time	1	2	3	4	5	DK
This workshop increased my understanding of this project	1	2	3	4	5	DK
This workshop clearly explained compound flooding	1	2	3	4	5	DK
This workshop clearly explained traditional flood mitigation strategies	1	2	3	4	5	DK
This workshop clearly explained natural and nature-based features (NNBFs) as flood mitigation strategies	1	2	3	4	5	DK
This workshop increased my knowledge about modeling capabilities and constraints for this project	1	2	3	4	5	DK
I learned something that I will apply to my current or future work	1	2	3	4	5	DK

3) What did you like most about the workshop? Please explain.

4) What aspect of this workshop was least useful to you? Please explain.

5) What improvements would you recommend in this workshop?

6) What questions, if any, do you have because of participating in this workshop?

Appendix B: Workshop Presentations

Coastal Nature Based Solutions to Mitigate Flood Impacts and Enhance Resilience

Hamed Moftakhari, Ph.D., P.E.

Center for ComplexHydroSystems Research

Department of Civil, Construction, and Environmental Engineering

The University of Alabama

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WHERE LEGENDS ARE MADE™

Value of NBS

Value of Coastal Wetland Habitat

Coastal wetlands filter our water, protect our coastal communities from floods, and provide habitat for fish and other wildlife—but they're quickly disappearing. NOAA is working hard to protect and restore these valuable habitats.

Wetlands Working for You

Wetlands—including marshes, mangroves, and swamps—provide valuable benefits to people, wildlife, and communities.

Wetlands act as "nature's kidneys" to filter and absorb pollution.

\$23 billion in annual coastal protection services are provided by wetlands.

1.5 million gallons of floodwater can be stored by one acre of wetlands.

During storms, coastal wetlands absorb floods and wave energy, decreasing property damage by up to **20%**.

8.1 million tons of CO₂ are absorbed by U.S. wetlands each year. That's equivalent to more than 900 million gallons of gas.

Wetlands provide key habitat and nursery grounds for valuable wildlife like shrimp, salmon, and crabs.

Habitat at Risk

80,000 acres

of wetlands in U.S. coastal watersheds may be lost each year to development, drainage, erosion, and sinking. That's approximately **seven football fields** every hour.

Our Work

NOAA works with our partners to protect valuable wetlands.

50,000 acres of wetland habitat have been restored by NOAA since 2008.

More information: <https://fisheries.noaa.gov/habitat-conservation>

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Value of NBS

Costanza et al., 2021 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.10237>

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In Mobile Bay

About half a football field of marshes on the edges of Mobile Bay vanished annually over the past four decades!

Nearly a third of Mobile Bay marshes gone since 1980s!

IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing

Fusing Multisource Data to Estimate the Effects of Urbanization, Sea Level Rise, and Hurricane Impacts on Long-Term Wetland Change Dynamics

David F. Mufoz ; Paul Mufoz ; Abieh Alipour ; Hamed Mofakheri ; Hamid Moradkhani ; Behzad Mortazavi

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Project Objectives

- 1) Quantify the performance of natural features and nature-based solutions, including wetland restoration projects, in mitigating compound flood impacts to residents of Mobile Bay
- 2) Provide actionable data to decision makers and help them more efficiently allocate resources to achieve greater resilience of coastal communities against flooding through nature-based solutions

Project Flowchart

Thank you!

Hamed Moftakhari

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<https://twitter.com/hamedmoftakhari>

What is Compound Flooding?

Hamed Moftakhari, Ph.D., P.E.

Center for ComplexHydroSystemsResearch

Department of Civil, Construction, and Environmental Engineering

The University of Alabama

Hurricane Ian, Sep. 23^d – Oct. 2nd 2022

An overall count of 148 deaths related to Hurricane Ian being reported, 119 of those deaths were caused by the flooding, winds and other dangerous conditions during the storm. <https://www.nbcnews.com/news/aeews/hurricaneian-florida-death-toll-rcna54069>

Hurricane Ian may have caused \$67 billion in damage, a top 5 U.S. storm

Andrew Freedman, author of [Active Climate](#)

Hurricane Ian likely caused \$53 billion to \$74 billion in insured losses from Florida to the Carolinas, with a "best estimate" of \$67 billion, according to [new data](#) released today from modeling firm RMS.

Introduction

Challenges

Opportunities

Tropical Cyclone

Hurricane Ida (Aug 26 – Sep 4, 2021)

Compound floods

IPCC SREX:

- Two or more simultaneous or successive extreme events
- Combinations of extreme events with underlying conditions that amplify the impact
- Combinations of events that are not themselves extremes but lead to an extreme event or impact when combined

What's wrong?

Facing the Challenge of Urban Flooding in the United States

Facing the Challenge of Urban Flooding in the United States

BOX 2.1 Hurricane Harvey

A little more than a month after the committee visited Houston, the city was struck by Hurricane Harvey (Figure 2.1.1). The Harris County Flood Control District estimates that the heavy rainfall over the 4-day period was between a 3,000-year and 20,000-year event (Lindner and Fitzgerald, 2018). The District also estimates that 154,170 homes were flooded in Harris County during this event, including 48,850 homes within the 100-year floodplain, 34,970 homes between the 100- and 500-year floodplains, and 70,370 homes (46 percent) outside the 500-year floodplain. A similar analysis by the city of Houston estimates that 208,353 households were affected, including 123,790 (59 percent) outside the 500-year floodplain (City of Houston Housing and Community Development, 2018). Hence, it can be concluded that approximately half of the homes in Houston affected by flooding from Hurricane Harvey were outside the mapped floodplains. Before Hurricane Harvey occurred in 2017, the benchmark rainstorm event in Houston was Tropical Storm Allison in 2001, which dropped less rain and inundated a smaller area, flooding approximately 73,000 homes.

BOX 2.1 Hurricane Harvey

A little more than a month after the committee visited Houston, the city was struck by Hurricane Harvey (Figure 2.1.1). The Harris County Flood Control District estimates that the heavy rainfall over the 4-day period was between a 3,000-year and 20,000-year event (Lindner and Fitzgerald, 2018). The District also estimates that 154,170 homes were flooded in Harris County during this event, including 48,850 homes within the 100-year floodplain, 34,970 homes between the 100- and 500-year floodplains, and 70,370 homes (46 percent) outside the 500-year floodplain. A similar analysis by the city of Houston estimates that 208,353 households were affected, including 123,790 (59 percent) outside the 500-year floodplain (City of Houston Housing and Community Development, 2018). Hence, it can be concluded that approximately half of the homes in Houston affected by flooding from Hurricane Harvey were outside the mapped floodplains. Before Hurricane Harvey occurred in 2017, the benchmark rainstorm event in Houston was Tropical Storm Allison in 2001, which dropped less rain and inundated a smaller area, flooding approximately 73,000 homes.

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Probability 101

• Univariate

10^4

$$EP = \frac{1}{RP} = 1 - CDF$$

$$RP = 100\text{yrs}$$

$$EP = 0.01 = 1\%$$

$$CDF = 0.99$$

• Bivariate

wikimediaorg

Joint PDF

Joint CDF

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Guidelines?

NOAA Atlas 14
Precipitation-Frequency Atlas
of the United States

Volume 11 Version 2.0: Texas

Sanja Perica, Sandra Pavlovic, Michael St. Laurent,
Carl Tryppakuk, Dale Unruh, Orlan Withe

U.S. Department
of Commerce
National Oceanic
and Atmospheric
Administration
National Weather
Service
Silver Spring,
Maryland, 2019

Guidance for Flood Risk
Analysis and Mapping

Coastal Flood Frequency and
Extreme Value Analysis

November 2016

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Probabilistic modeling

25 yrs rainfall
+
25 yr surg
=
A 100 yr compound flood

A 100 yr compound flood is going to be a 25 yr event on each margin!

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Process-based modeling

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Process-based modeling

3D-view of Mobile Bay downtown, AL.

Hydrodynamic model output for Mobile Bay

Max. floodwater depth for Hurricane Nate, Oct/2017.

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Thank you!

Hamed Moftakhari

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<https://twitter.com/hamedmoftakhari>

NBS Mitigation Strategies

Overview

1. NBS Design Alternatives
2. Modeling goals
3. Modeling scenario scope

[USDOT, 2019](#)

Engineering Design Alternatives: Shades of Grey to Green

MARSH (VEGETATION)

The construction of a marsh, including fill and plantings but without structural elements, in the intertidal zone of a shoreline.

Design Schematics

[USDOT, 2019](#)

Marsh Restoration/Creation

MARSH (BREAKWATER)

The construction of a marsh, including fill and plantings, in the intertidal zone of a shoreline, including segmented breakwaters to reduce incident wave energy.

Design Schematics

[USDOT, 2019](#)

Marsh Restoration/Creation

MARSH (SILL)

The construction of a marsh, including fill and plantings, fronted by toe protection in the intertidal zone of a shoreline.

Design Schematics

[USDOT, 2019](#)

Marsh Restoration/Creation

Engineered Structures

Munoz et al., 2019

Broad modeling goals: Exam the impact of NBS alternatives on flood hazards

Scope of Modeling

- Grid size: 10m x 10m
- Temporal scale: Design storms
- NBS Representation:
 - Hydrodynamic simulations
 - Static representation
 - Generalizable results

Munoz et al., 2019

Appendix C: Summary of Collected Feedback

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Ice Breaker, Rainfall Events Discussion

Discussion Summary:

In the discussion following the ice breaker activity, attendees provided feedback on the types of storm events that they would like to see used for model calibration and validation (Fig C1). Some people also shared types of storms or rain events for which they would like more accurate model predictions. There was agreement that model predictions for the common intense spring rains that occur in the Mobile area would be useful. Storms that surpass predicted surge, rainfall, or intensity were also suggested as the types of storms attendees are interested in, like Zeta in 2020. Others suggested consecutive events that occur in quick succession, and events that occur in consecutive years. Some of the named storms that produced record precipitation, like Danny and Sally were suggested to use for model calibration. Two rainfall events were suggested as possible events to use for model calibration: an April 2014 storm and a December 2016 storm. Finally, CoCoRaHS was shared as a source to find rainfall information (<https://www.cocorahs.org/>).

Figure C1: Storm event discussion notes

Flood Mapping

The purpose of this activity was to gather as much information as possible about where flooding occurs and the effect of that flooding. Participants dictated the details about flooding locations to a facilitator who input the information into Survey 123. After initial mapping, the full bay map was projected on the wall for everyone to see. When asked if any areas were missing, suggestions were made to add part of Yancy Branch, highway 43 in Chickasaw and county highways 10/12 in South Baldwin County. Renee added the suggested areas into Survey123 so they would populate on the projected map. Attention was drawn to areas of sparse flooding, like Daphne and Spanish Fort that experience rainfall flooding but not tidally driven flooding. It was brought up that much of Bon Secour floods, but the homes are elevated so minimal damage occurs; however, road access to some properties is impeded. Drawn flood locations are shown in blue on figures C2, C3, C4 and C5. This data was used to develop a GIS web map along with the map points in later mitigation mapping activities.

Figure C2: Flood locations drawn on Mobile Bay Survey123 map

Figure C3: Zoomed-in view of area north of Mobile

Figure C4: Zoomed-in view of the middle section of Fig C2

Figure C5: Zoomed-in view of the southernmost section of Fig C2

Defining Compound Flooding

In the Q&A following Hamed’s presentation on compound flooding, a question was asked about the ability of gauges to predict compound flooding. Hamed explained that a gauge may capture some drivers but not all of them and that multiple different sensors would be needed to capture different drivers. Another question asked was whether flood drivers can be separated in the model, and it was explained that they can be separated. To set the rainfall axis boundaries, one person pointed out that design standards are typically 10-15 years in their line of work. First it was suggested to set the upper boundary for rainfall at 50 years, but it was brought up that some infrastructure is planned for a 100-year event. After some back-and-forth, the group settled on setting the low boundary on the rainfall (Y) axis at 2 and the high boundary at 100.

It was more difficult for the group to decide on boundaries for surge, some suggested a 250-year event, but Hamed pointed out the data record is not long enough to support that and the level of uncertainty would be too high. The surge (X) axis was set at 1 for the low boundary and 100 for the upper boundary. Each attendee was given 3 dots: 1 red high-priority, 1 yellow medium-priority, and 1 green lower-priority.

Figure C6: Graph with return periods for coastal flooding on X axis and return periods for rainfall on the Y axis

Some clusters were apparent on the graph, indicating agreement on priorities. Renee circled the 5 cluster priorities that emerged. The most distinct cluster was made up of 5 red high-priority, dots in a low surge/intermediate rainfall area on the graph. The approximate return periods were about 5 for surge and 50 for rainfall. Two clusters were evident on the 50-year surge line, one at about 50 and the other at 25 for rainfall. There were no dots greater than about 60 for rainfall and very few dots below 10 years. It was clear most participants priorities lie in the 20–50-year range for rainfall. Similar patterns emerged for surge return periods, there was minimal interest in high return periods with most of the dots in about the 20–50-year range.

Renee pointed out that the low return periods came up often in earlier discussion but did not get many dots during the activity. She also pointed out some of the clear clustering in the 50/50 area of the graph. Hamed brought up the concept of cumulative impact of the flood drivers and whether more events with lower return periods should be considered. Renee asked the group if the lower return periods should be given more consideration. One person suggested merging the 25/25 cluster with the 50/50 cluster.

Future Planning

In this section, attendees were asked to place sticker dots to indicate planning priorities for three different categories: Design Life, SLR trends, and Percent increase in Extreme Rainfall. For SLR trends out to 2050 (Fig C7), dots were evenly spread between Intermediate-High, High, and Current Trend with just a few dots placed at intermediate. Beyond 2050, almost half of the dots were placed at the Intermediate-High level and about a third were placed at High. One dot was placed on Intermediate Low, and a few dots were placed on Intermediate.

Figure C7: Percent of respondents planning for each SLR trend level out to 2050 and beyond 2050

To understand the percent increase in extreme rainfall for which stakeholders are planning, another line was drawn with 10%, 15%, and 20% as the options (Fig C8). Almost half of the respondents indicated they are planning for a 15% increase. A few indicated they are not planning for any increase in extreme rainfall events. More than a third of respondents

indicated they are planning for a 10% increase in extreme rainfall and a few people indicated they are planning for an increase greater than 15%.

Figure C9: Lifespan for which projects are being designed

Lastly, participants selected design life for which they are building projects (Fig C9). About a third of respondents placed dots on the 30-year line and another third placed their dots on the 50-year line. After the charts were marked, a short discussion was held to review the responses.

Mitigation Mapping

The purpose of this section was to allow participants to mark different features throughout the modeling domain. There were 9 maps of the bay, labeled A through I with Map A being the Alabama Port area just north of Dauphin Island. Map labeling continued clockwise around the bay with Fort Morgan Peninsula on map I. All 9 were displayed in each of the two conference rooms and the attendees were divided between the two rooms. Groupings were loosely based the areas in which people work. In one room were folks that work on projects throughout both counties. In the other room were people that work predominantly in one county or the other. Past mitigation efforts were marked with blue dots, future mitigation projects with pink dots, changes in land use or zoning with green dots and areas information is needed with orange dots (Fig C10). Project details were noted for each dot, including the date of implementation, size, criteria for success, what it would look like if no action is taken, and if any pre- or post- monitoring is being conducted. Over 50 points were identified across all maps. A GIS web map was created with the map points from this activity and the previous Survey123 flood mapping activity. To request the web map, please contact Hamed Moftakhari at hmoftakhari@eng.ua.edu or Larisa Lee at Larisa.Lee@msstate.edu.

Figure C10: Example of a map showing color coded points

Outputs/End Products

Feedback was collected regarding outputs and end products stakeholders would find most useful. Questions were written on flip charts and attendees independently wrote responses to the questions on post-it notes (Fig C11).

Answers to the first question, “What could you do with this kind of information?” seemed to fit into three common themes: management, communication, and project prioritization/design. To use the information from the project as justification or leverage was also suggested. For the second question, “How do you need this info packaged?”, there were

many suggestions for maps, shapefiles, and simulations. It was also recommended to make sure the information is digestible by non-experts or landowners/public. Answers to the third question, "Where do you go now to get this type of information?" listed mainly online tools, the FEMA website, and other coastal resource managers. Regarding integrating project outputs with what currently exists, it was suggested to integrate with county websites.

Figure C11: Example of participant responses grouped on a chart

Appendix D: Glossary of Acronyms

Acronym List

ADCNR – Alabama Department of Conservation and Natural Resources

AL – Alabama

MSU – Mississippi State University

NBS – Nature Based Solution

NERR – National Estuarine Research Reserve

NOAA – National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

NWR – National Wildlife Refuge

USGS – United States Geological Survey

USFWS – United States Fish and Wildlife Service